

EARTH SCIENCES

HISTORICAL ROADS OF GEORGIA AND PROSPECTS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE MIDDLE CORRIDOR (BETWEEN EUROPE AND ASIA)

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Abstract

The relevance of the article is related to the geographical characteristics of historical roads. In this regard, this issue has not been studied so far, which was done according to the work. Connecting with each other. An in-depth study of the issue will become a prerequisite for better interconnection of regions and their economic development. It is also possible to increase the transit role of Georgia and use its geographical location. The goals and objectives of the work are related to the relevance of the topic. The objectives of the research include: studying the history of historical roads in Georgia and revealing their significance; identifying the geographical characteristics of historical roads in the world and in Georgia; studying international, regional and local roads in Georgia and revealing their geographical characteristics; discussing historical roads in a geopolitical context; studying the prospects for their restoration, which can become a prerequisite for the development of a particular region of the country and the implementation of infrastructure projects.

Keywords: historical roads, Georgia, Middle Corridor, Europe-Asia, transit.

1. Introduction

Georgia is geographically located between Europe and Asia, almost completely surrounded by Russia and former socialist states. The geographical and political interests of these countries, relations with military blocs, the existing political and economic situation, military confrontation, form of government, ethnic and religious composition determine the rather complex nature of Georgia's geopolitical location. Georgia is located in a geopolitical space where the Christian and Muslim worlds are intertwined, which to some extent affects the political processes currently taking place in the Caucasus region. Georgia has a rather favorable transport and geographical location between Europe and Asia. Due to this, Georgia serves as an important corridor of the Europe-Asia transport corridor. Its importance is reflected in the economic and political relations between the countries of the Caucasus and its adjacent regions. The country's maritime (in the Atlantic Ocean) location also plays a significant role, which connects Georgia to most of the world's countries. The Europe-Asia pipeline and railway transport already play a major role in the development of transport links, which increases cargo and passenger turnover. Currently, Georgia's transport and geographical location is becoming particularly important in the economic and political relations of a number of regions of the world.

2021). The country's maritime location also plays an important role, thanks to which Georgia connects China and the countries of Central Asia with Europe in the shortest way. Road, pipeline and railway transport connecting Europe and Asia play a major role in the development of transport links, which increases the indicators of cargo turnover and passenger turnover, and Georgias place in world economic relations. Some characteristics of the country's geographical location

(especially political and transport-geographical) are variable factors in space and time. They have been changing over the centuries under the influence of political, military, economic and demographic processes.

Currently, a number of characteristics of Georgia's geographical location and the growing interest in the restoration of historical routes between Europe and Asia can be effectively used for the sustainable development of the country.[1,2,3,4]

While much is made of contemporary development projects all across the Middle Corridor, a historical analysis of ancient trade routes shows the durability of the path through Georgia. Contemporary Georgia is at a crossroads, where many possible development directions depend on international appreciation of its value as a throughway between Europe and Asia. The aim of the article is to show the significance of Georgian historical roads in the development of the middle Corridor.

Georgia was a favorable place because it connected Europe and Asia by the shortest route. The climatic conditions here were more comfortable for caravans. Accordingly, the Silk Road, a system of caravan routes that reached from China to the Mediterranean, passed here.

Herodotus wrote about the road connecting the Sea of Azov and Central Asia. He also mentioned the Imperial Road, which connected Asia Minor with Iran. Further east, the Lapis Lazuli Road operated, through which this mineral reached Assyria, Egypt, and China from the Badakhshan mountains. Further north, the Western Meridian Road is noteworthy, which connected Central Asia and Southern Siberia with China during the Qin Empire. Also important was the Steppe Road, which connected East Turkestan via the Volga region to the Greek colonies on the Black Sea. It is

therefore conceivable that a section of this road also passed through Georgia. According to Chinese chronicles and ancient sources, it is established that the Silk Road ran north of Lake Lob-Nor, through Kuchi and Karashar, then crossed the Tian Shan and went to Fer-

gana via the Terskedivan Pass, then crossed the Southern Urals, the Lower Volga region and reached the northern Black Sea coast, or from Fergana it passed through Samarkand, the Amur Darya and ended in Iran and Asia Minor.

Figure 1 silk road main and secondary routes [8. <https://transportgeography.org>]

3. Research methods

When working on the article, geographical, geopolitical, cartographic and comparative analysis methods were used. Special attention was paid to the analysis of scientific and historical literature, which reflects the peculiarities of Georgia's geopolitical and transport-geographical location. Also the research was done by the author in the various regions of Georgia and locals were asked to show the main routes which connected settlements. While working on the article, both Georgian and English-language, scientific literature was used systematization and classification of the received information.

The silk road – history and modern day

The Silk Road routes included a large network of strategically located trading posts, markets and thoroughfares designed to streamline the transport, exchange, distribution and storage of goods.

Routes extended from the Greco-Roman metropolis of Antioch across the Syrian Desert via Palmyra to Ctesiphon (the Parthian capital) and Seleucia on the Tigris River, a Mesopotamian city in modern-day Iraq. From Seleucia, routes passed eastward over the Zagros Mountains to the cities of Ecbatana (Iran) and Merv (Turkmenistan), from which additional routes traversed to modern-day Afghanistan and eastward into Mongolia and China. Silk Road routes also led to ports on the Persian Gulf, where goods were then transported up the Tigris and Euphrates rivers. Routes from these cities also connected to ports along the Mediterranean Sea, from which goods were shipped to cities throughout the Roman Empire and into Europe. [5]

Georgia was a favorable place because it connected Europe and Asia by the shortest route. The climatic conditions here were more comfortable for caravans. Accordingly, the Silk Road, a system of caravan routes that reached from China to the Mediterranean, passed here. Herodotus wrote about the road connecting the Sea of Azov and Central Asia. He also mentioned the Imperial Road, which connected Asia Minor with Iran. Further east, the Lapis Lazuli Road operated, through which this mineral reached Assyria, Egypt, and China from the Badakhshan mountains. Further north, the Western Meridian Road is noteworthy, which connected Central Asia and Southern Siberia with China during the Qin Empire. The Great Road began in Xian from Dunkhuan. It branched off to the west in two directions. Both roads - the first north of Lake Lobnor through Turpan, and the second south of the same lake through Notan and Yarkand - converged in Kashgar. From here, the road to the north connected with Transcaucasia via the Caspian Sea, crossed Georgia, and from Phasis via the Black Sea to Byzantium and Rome. It is interesting to see what territories the historical road from the Caspian Sea to the Black Sea passed through. One road went through Derbent and Magas (North Caucasus) to Sukhumi, from where the sea route began, while the second road started in Iran from Ardabil and then passed through Ganja, Tbilisi, Mtskheta and Gori. From here, through Kutaisi and Poti to the Black Sea it was connected to a shipping route that first reached Trabzon and then to Istanbul.

Then during the 16th centuries this route was abandoned and used only by the Ottomans [5]

Figure 2 Georgian medieval roads (4th-16th centuries)

Discussion

Similarly to the ancient Silk Road, it is often compared to, the Middle Corridor is more of a network of interconnected routes than a single, neatly delineated corridor. A main artery runs through Kazakhstan, Uzbekistan, and Turkmenistan, crosses the Caspian Sea to Azerbaijan, Georgia, and the Black Sea on its way into Europe: a total of about 4,250km of rail lines and 500km of sea transport. Alternatives include routes through Iran and Turkey that need no ferries. This amounts to about 2,000km less than the Eurasian Northern Corridor, as well as (if all goes to schedule) transit time savings of about a week—or more than three weeks when compared to the southern sea route that transits the Suez Canal. It is incorrect to conflate the Middle Corridor, as observers sometimes do, with China's Belt and Road Initiative (BRI). The main difference is that the Middle Corridor is primarily of concern to Central Asia, while the BRI is both larger in geographic scope and seen as a conduit of Chinese influence. There is, nevertheless, considerable overlap – commentators are quick to point out that back in 2013, Kazakhstan and Nazarbayev personally played a key role in the launching of the BRI in the capital Astana as a kind of progenitor to the Middle Corridor – and today, funds from the BRI are expected to flow into the TITR.

“Much of what was discussed at the [2023 China-Central Asia] summit in Xi'an, China, included plans to upgrade bilateral investment agreements and increase cross-border freight volume between China and Central Asia,” says Felix Chang, a senior Asia expert at US-based think tank Foreign Policy Research Institute [6]

5. Conclusions

Geographically, Georgia is located on the border of Europe and Asia, with almost complete isolation from Russia and the socialist orientation of the Sahel. The country's geographical and political interests, relations with military blocs, political and economic relations, military confrontation, military form, ethnic and religious relations create a rather complex geopolitical situation [1,2,3,4]

Georgia's geopolitical location is negatively affected by the ethnic, religious or territorial conflicts that are taking place in the Caucasus region and its immediate surroundings. Currently, the conflict regions are Abkhazia, Ossetia and Ingushetia, Nagorno-Karabakh, Ukraine and Russia, Israel and Iran. Some of them significantly affect the socio-economic development of the country and the effective implementation of the state strategy for sustainable development. Georgia can become one of the alternative branches of the Silk Road, because during the war it is a convenient and safe direction for connecting Europe and Asia through the Caspian and Black Seas. Its use is especially important in the background of the Russia-Ukraine war, when it became necessary to connect Central Asia and Eastern Europe with alternative routes. It is also possible to lay new gas and oil pipelines in order to reduce dependence on Russia. [1,2,3,4]

The Russian-Ukrainian and USA-Iran war significantly affected the transport and geographical location of Georgia. The cargo turnover between the countries of the North and South, the West and the East (Europe and Asia) has increased significantly. The reason for this is that Georgias transport and geographical location

between Europe and Asia. The European-Asian transport corridor plays an important role in the economic and political development of the Caucasus and its adjacent regions (Elizbarashvili et al., Public

Geography of Georgia, 2021). The country's maritime location also plays a role, which connects China and the countries of Central Asia with Europe in the shortest way. Road, pipeline and rail transport connecting Europe and Asia play a major role in the development of transport links, which increases the indicators of cargo turnover and passenger turnover, and Georgia's place in world economic relations. Some features of the geographical location (especially political and transport-geography) is variable factors in space and time. They have been changing over the centuries under the influence of political, military, economic or demographic processes. Currently, a number of features of the geographical location of Georgia and the growing interest in the restoration of historical routes between Europe and Asia can be effectively used for the sustainable development of the country. Especially when the conflict between Ukraine and Russia is unsolved and Iran- USA War has just started.[7]

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